

THE ROLE OF PROFESSIONAL REFLECTION IN THE PEDAGOGICAL ACTIVITY OF A PRIMARY CLASS TEACHER

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Abstract. *This article describes how to improve the organization and management of reflective thinking among elementary school teachers, analyzing information and prioritizing substantive relationships in joint actions.*

Keywords: *professional reflection, literacy, analytical thinking, objective assessment, analysis, conclusion, planning, motivation.*

In the world, education appears as the main factor that ensures the development of a person. In the international concept of education set by UNESCO until 2030, "quality education promotes creative thinking and knowledge, develops the foundations of literacy and numeracy skills, as well as analytical, problem-solving, reasoning and other interpersonal and social skills at a high level. guarantees possession» [1], it is noted. This determines the development of reflexive skills such as creative thinking, critical thinking, self-evaluation, understanding of historical reality, and analysis of one's own activities among students in the general secondary education system. The analysis of pedagogical experiences at the international level shows that the development of strategies for improving the processes of formation of reflexive skills in students and the design of mechanisms for its implementation are of great importance in ensuring the effectiveness of education. In the processes of formation of reflexive skills in teachers of general secondary educational institutions, the teacher thinks more analytically about himself and independently assimilates the new concepts being studied by himself. that is, it takes place in independent thought processes when the teacher is not traditionally taught by the student. Encouraging primary school teachers to self-analysis, objective assessment of their concepts, activities and activities, i.e. reflexive activity, to study history, the conditions of the period before the independence of our country and creates situations encouraging to study, analyze and objectively assess the historical way of life of our ancestors. Therefore, in order to develop reflexive skills in teachers, it is important to consider the following processes as directions of their reflexive activity:

1. Self-analysis and objective assessment: analysis of one's own concepts and perceptions; comparing one's understanding, imagination and behavior with the understanding, imagination and behavior of peers and siblings; objective assessment of one's actions; analyze how one is perceived by peers, comrades and other people; understanding and self-control with whom one interacts in the process of communication.

2. Comparison, analysis, objective assessment and conclusion of the past (history) with the present: study of the relationship between the past and the present in relation to the studied concepts; their comparison, analysis and objective assessment; formation of objective ideas about independence, its essence, importance and necessity; formation and development of reflexive activity skills. In order to form a conscious discipline instead of forced obedience in the processes of formation and development of reflexive skills in elementary school teachers, it is necessary to take into account the following features specific to these processes: the teacher's activity with

students is a unique integrative system; interdependence of students' inclinations, personal capabilities, initial concepts and personal interests; Disproportion of effectiveness with gradualism (paying special attention or not paying attention to an active student or group of students) in the processes of formation and development of reflexive skills in teachers; the need to create a reflexive educational environment in educational institutions; that the processes of educational relations are of practical importance. The process of forming reflexive skills in students is a complex pedagogical system that covers a wide range of features specific to the system. On the other hand, in this system, social-psychological functions are implemented by teachers in the process of effective performance of their functional tasks.

This great sense of responsibility requires teachers to improve various processes of pedagogical skills at the level of modern requirements. In recent years, pedagogues and psychologists have emphasized the importance of developing thinking and analytical skills in the pedagogical activity of teachers. The basis of these abilities is the teacher's professional reflection. Reflection (lat. "reflexio" - to go back) is "a form of theoretical activity aimed at understanding the behavior of a well-developed person and their laws; is an activity aimed at self-knowledge and understanding, which reveals the unique hidden features of the human spiritual world.

For the first time, the concept of reflection arose in ancient Greek philosophy and meant drawing attention to the thoughts of a person in his mind, the process of his thinking, the analysis of the content of his thoughts. Socrates, Plato, Locke and other Greek philosophers emphasize that reflection is the activity of a person aimed at self-knowledge and recognition of what he is capable of. European philosophers such as Kant, Hegel, Fichte, and Schelling viewed reflection as a basis for the development of human cognitive abilities. According to Leibniz's concept, reflection is mentioned as a feature of human ability to apperception (the dependence of perception on human past experience and individual characteristics).

In today's modern philosophy, reflection is distinguished between theoretical and practical aspects. The first is the process of development of concepts by a person, as a method that gives the opportunity to move from one definition to another within the framework of a single concept; and the second is the process of attributing an individual action or thought to a concept, in which control over the scale of attribution must be ensured.

Currently, reflection, which is studied as a philosophical category, is recognized and researched as a research object of psychology, sociology, synergetics, logic, andrology, eucistics, cybernetics and many other complex sciences. We define the category of "reflection" from the point of view of pedagogy and psychology, and while studying its essence, we analyze in detail its place in the professional activity of teachers.

In psychology, reflection is interpreted as "the subject's knowledge and control of his internal mental processes and states." In the pedagogical activity of the teacher, in the study of the importance of reflection in relation to the person, it is recognized that the definition of this concept is perfect from a social psychological point of view, in which reflection is considered as how a person is perceived and evaluated by other people in existence: reflection is "just a sub" It involves not the act's self-knowledge or understanding, but how others "know the ``reflective'" and understand his/her personality traits, emotional reactions, and cognitive representations.

Scientifically studying the possibilities of managing a person's psychic development, S. L. Rubinstein connects human existence and his relationship to social existence with reflection:

"Reflection is a process that stops and interrupts the continuous life process of a person for a moment and takes a person out of its boundaries in imagination. In this situation, every action of a person acquires a certain character of philosophical thoughts about life."

By studying the reflection in human thinking that occurs when solving creative problems, scientists identify it as the self-management method of the thinking subject (Y.N. Kulyutkin, S.Yu. Stepanov, etc.), the factor of critical thinking (I.N.Semyonov), theoretically evaluate it as a high indicator of thinking (A.Z.Zak, V.V.Davidov, etc.).

I.S. Ladenko connects the importance of reflection in the self-organization of intellectual systems with the need to improve the skills and abilities of intellectual activity and the need to develop psychological views about the internal and external forms of speech, memory, imagination. He said, "Reflection is the basis for forming thoughts about the transition from internal imagination to external imagination and vice versa, the internalization of these processes (transition of external factors to internal factors) in the process of thinking... Based on reflection, not only psychological knowledge, but also memory, skills and abilities will be formed and methods of practical application will be improved. In current modern pedagogical research, many scientists rely on the classification of reflection proposed by I.N. Semyonov.

Ensuring the effectiveness of the processes of forming reflexive skills in teachers in all aspects, in the processes of planning, organizing, motivating and controlling information analysis, target-motivation, foresight-planning, organizational-executive by leaders, specialists and teachers, effective implementation of control-diagnosis, regulation-coordination functions is envisaged. The essence and importance of the implementation of these functions is expressed in the following processes: planning processes of formation and development of reflexive skills; ensuring the activity of teachers and forming their interest in learning; to harmonize the set goals and available opportunities with the interests and needs of students; to stimulate students' level of basic concepts, abilities, personal feelings, interests, as well as reflexive activities based on coordination, control, analysis and objective assessment.

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